

AquaPLAN

Aquatic Pollution from Light and
Anthropogenic Noise: **Management
of Impacts on Biodiversity**

D3.3 Harmonised protocols for monitoring LNP impact in aquatic systems

11/11/2024 Version 2.4.

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Public¹

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1.3	27/06/2024	UNIFI	Elena Maggi	Paragraph "Data Management"
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2.3	27/06/2024	UNIFI	Alessandro Marchetti	Update tables
2.4	11/11/2024	UOP	Thomas Davies Mascha Stroobant	Layout and minor corrections

PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The AquaPLAN project promises to establish the first long term monitoring survey of the biological impacts of Light and Noise Pollution (LNP) across European aquatic ecosystems. Observational field studies of the combined impacts of LNP have not previously been attempted, providing no baseline to guide investigators towards a harmonized monitoring approach. This deliverable outlines a suite of harmonized monitoring protocols that AquaPLAN investigators will use as a guide when designing observational field studies, collecting data and curating data for the long-term benefit of the AquaPLAN project and other users. The deliverable is partnered with D3.1, which outlines harmonized monitoring protocols for the collection of physical LNP data in the field. D3.3 will guide AquaPLAN investigators in conducting field surveys that will lead to the completion of D3.9 “Database of ecological time series (spanning sometimes three years), or paired sampling of spatial comparisons, relating biodiversity changes to LNP conditions (including the Essential Biodiversity Variables responses and data on stressors)” and 3.10 “Report (including crossed-system analyses) on results on potential impacts of LNP on rivers, lakes, temperate and tropical coastal systems”.

D3.3 has been prepared in collaboration with all AquaPLAN investigators involved in the collection of biological data in field experiments (Task 3.3). A series of meetings were held in the first 6 months of the AquaPLAN project to agree a strategy towards D3.3, identify issues to be considered in the harmonized protocols, discuss and agree protocols that address identified issues, review planned field activities and review the draft report for D3.3 (**Table 1**).

Table 1. Activities leading to the completion of D3.3

Date	Duration	Item discussed	Partners invited
02/02/2024	1 hour	Strategy for delivering harmonized monitoring protocols	SZN, UOP
22/02/2024	2 hours	Identify issues in the development of harmonized monitoring protocols	UOP, SZN, UNIFI, FVB-IGB, BIU, ULEI
27/03/2024	2 hours	Discuss issues in the development of harmonized monitoring protocols	UOP, SZN, UNIFI, FVB-IGB, BIU, ULEI
24/04/2024	2 hours	Peer review of planned monitoring activities that lead to deliverables in Task 3.3	UOP, SZN, UNIFI, FVB-IGB, BIU, ULEI, PML, CSIC, IMR
15/05/2024	2 hours	Peer review of planned monitoring activities that lead to deliverables in Task 3.3	UOP, SZN, UNIFI, FVB-IGB, BIU, ULEI, PML, CSIC, IMR
07/06/2024	1 hour	Harmonize reporting approach to D3.1, D3.3 and D4.1.	UOP, SZN, UNIFI, FVB-IGB
14/06/2024	2 hours	Review draft report of D3.1, D3.3 and D4.1.	UOP, SZN, UNIFI, FVB-IGB, BIU, ULEI, PML, CSIC, IMR

Disclaimer: The document does not in any way overrule the Grant Agreement (including its associated Annexes) and the Consortium Agreement.

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1. INTRODUCTION

LNP impacts on aquatic organisms are well established. A broad array of species and biological processes are impacted across all aquatic ecosystems. Either light or noise pollution can impact all aspects of organism life histories from early developmental phases up to reproductive maturity. **This suggests that LNP is likely impacting population dynamics and the structure of ecological communities at large spatial and temporal scales.** The vast majority of LNP research however investigates individual responses to specific sensory stimuli over short time frames. Examples include behavioural responses of organisms to sounds from ships, pile driving, street lighting or skyglow. Long-term monitoring or targeted sampling surveys of biological responses to LNP are largely lacking, but critical for understanding how empirically demonstrated impacts on individuals shape broadscale ecological patterns and processes over time and space.

The AquaPLAN project was designed in part to address the question of whether LNP shapes ecological systems over large spatial and temporal scales. To achieve this, AquaPLAN investigators will implement a novel monitoring programme, aimed at creating a variety of long-term ecological time series and spatial sampling designs for detecting and quantifying emerging, combined impacts of LNP on key aquatic habitats: rivers, lakes, temperate and tropical coastal systems (T3.3). The monitoring programme will be established in the first six months of the project, with field surveys conducted annually over three years. D3.1 and D3.3 describe the harmonized monitoring protocols to be implemented where possible during the collection of physical LNP data and biological response data respectively.

Several critical factors were considered during meetings leading to D3.3 (see **Table 1**). These included identifying the variety of abiotic and biotic parameters that should be considered when conducting LNP field surveys, the experimental design of studies capable of quantifying the biological impacts of light and noise pollution, and their combined impacts, the variety of biological responses to be measured across the AquaPLAN experimental systems, data collection protocols, metadata collection, and data collation and curation for further analysis.

While these protocols are designed to guide AquaPLAN investigators in quantifying biological responses to LNP in the real world, the issues considered, and protocols outlined are applicable to other investigators who plan to conduct similar studies. The protocols outlined in D3.3 have therefore been made publicly available so that they can provide a basis for the design of future LNP monitoring studies.

2. PARAMETERS CONSIDERED

AquaPLAN investigators discussed a broad array of parameters that should be considered when designing monitoring surveys of LNP biological impacts.

2.1 TARGET ORGANISM

- Experimental designs should account for the ecology of the focal taxa to be studied. Individuals can be **highly mobile covering distances >1km** in a day (fish, birds, mammals and turtles), **between 1km and 100m in a day** (fish, large crustaceans, cephalopods) or **distances less than 100m in a day** (most crustacean zooplankton, gastropods, amphipods, polychaete worms). Individuals can also be **sedentary** (bivalves) or **more often sessile** (barnacles, ascidians, bryozoans, sponges, corals)

and macrophytes). The mobility of a species has a strong influence on the independence of replicate sampling stations in space. Stations located within 100m of each other cannot be considered independent when the target species moves more than 100m in a day. Replication of stations sampling large mobile species should therefore be at larger spatial scales than less mobile species where possible. Notable exceptions to this may occur when monitoring behavioural responses of large mobile taxa (for example birds and marine mammals). In these instances, replication tends to be at the individual rather than in discrete spatial units.

- Investigators should consider whether impacts of LNP have been previously documented for the focal species or related taxa. Monitoring surveys are high effort and broad sweeps of all taxa present may prove inefficient.
- Where the composition of an entire ecological community is to be quantified, investigators should where possible consider the use of eDNA as an efficient sampling technique.
- Investigators should consider whether the focal taxa are **diurnal** (active during the day), **nocturnal** (active during the night), **catheimeral** (active at day and night) or **crepuscular** (active during twilight) when the response to be measured is **behavioural** (for example predation, activity, migration). Sampling of such taxa should focus on the time of day when they are most active in the first instance, although attempts should also be made to quantify the response across circadian and circalunar light cycles where possible for deeper insight or in critical phenological phases (dispersion, reproduction, foraging, commuting etc.). Where the effect of specific predictable noise or light events is to be measured, sampling should be scheduled before, during and after their occurrence to assess responses and effects.

2.2 RESPONSE TYPE

- The responses to be measured should be clearly defined into one of the Essential Biodiversity Variables (i.e. EBVs - **Table 2**).
- Responses can be measured from individuals (e.g. activity), populations (e.g. abundance) or ecological communities (e.g. species richness).
- Investigators are not expected to quantify every type of response in their respective experimental systems, rather they should sample responses that are scientifically appropriate and tractable.
- Investigators are advised to focus on measuring responses previously demonstrated to be impacted by LNP where possible.
- Investigators should measure responses appropriate to the spatial scale at which their monitoring survey is replicated.
- Behavioural responses should where possible be quantified both during the day and the night so that impacts on diel activity cycles can be reliably quantified.
- Where possible, nocturnal behavioural responses should be quantified across the lunar cycle.
- Investigators should consider whether the sampling techniques used to quantify responses reflect abundance or a combination of abundance and activity. Passive sampling techniques including fish traps, PIT tags, pitfall traps, underwater video⁵ sampling and potting all confound abundance with activity. All passive sampling techniques are valid for use in the AquaPLAN project; however, care should be taken

⁵ Please note that not all video studies are passive, vertical profilers for zooplankton used at IGB are instead active.

to design experiments where possible to account for the influence of circadian and circalunar activity cycles on the responses measured.

2.3 DISTRIBUTION OF LIGHT AND NOISE POLLUTION

- Investigators will use the available datasets of underwater ALAN (i.e. Artificial Light At Night) and ship noise (available from <https://aquaplan.eofrom.space/> and [JASCO NAVISON project – Mapping past and future shipping soundscapes of European seas](#)) to gain an insight into sampling design in the first instance. These maps are >1km resolution and the noise map does not account for localised sources from small and medium-sized vessel activities. The NAVISON maps will be available online later this year for all European seas in separate layers for five different vessel categories based on AIS data. However, rivers and lakes are not covered yet by this project, nor are non-AIS boats and other sound sources.
- Having identified suitable locations, AquaPLAN investigators will measure ALAN and noise pollution in situ to establish the level of exposure (see D3.1).

2.4 SUNLIGHT AND MOONLIGHT

- Sampling regimes should where possible account for sunlight and moonlight cycles.
- Times of sunrise and sunset, moonrise and moonset, and the illumination of the lunar disk can be obtained via www.timeanddate.com or using the Astropy package (Python and R).
- When measuring nocturnal responses, investigators should ensure the sun is >18 degrees below the horizon (astronomical twilight) where possible.
- Most nocturnal biological responses are actually crepuscular (occurring during twilight). Such responses should be measured after sunset and before sunrise.
- Responses that quantify abundances of sessile species or species that are nocturnally active but sedentary and conspicuous during the day, can be reliably quantified during daylight hours. This is particularly the case in rocky shore ecosystems where the daytime abundance of species is shaped in part by their activities during the night.
- Nighttime sampling is normally only required when measuring behavioural responses in nocturnal, crepuscular or cathemeral species.
- Sampling regimes should capture responses across the lunar phase cycle where possible. Typically, investigators would target sampling around the new moon and the full moon in the first instance with sampling during the quarter moons where possible. Where sampling efforts are restricted to one bout per month, investigators should consider whether the measured response is likely to be more prevalent during the full moon or the new moon.

2.5 TRACTABILITY

Investigators should ensure that the chosen taxa, responses and sampling design are tractable and can be repeated throughout the AquaPLAN project where required (once each year for each location). **Tractability** is critical to the longevity of long-term ecological time series. Expensive and resource-intensive sampling exercises are less likely to continue in the long term than a simple cost-effective approach.

3. SAMPLING DESIGN

- To reliably quantify the impacts of LNP in combination investigators should seek to sample across gradients of LNP that are not collinear (**Figure 1A**)
- To assist in the sampling design, investigators should consider categorizing sampling stations into a fully crossed experimental framework (**Figure 1B**).
- In the first instance, investigators can use available maps of ALAN and ship noise pollution to guide the selection of candidate sampling stations (<https://aquaplan.eofrom.space/>).
- Candidate sampling station selection should be validated using *in situ* measurements of LNP following the protocols outlined in D3.1.
- LNP can later be categorized according to the risk mapping approach produced by D3.4.
- Analyses of independent monitoring surveys can adopt the gradient, cross factored or risk mapping approach (**Figure 1C**) to defining the ALAN and noise pollution predictor variables.
- When using the cross-factored approach, a minimum of two sites should be sampled per treatment combination where possible.
- Researchers should seek where possible to sample multiple replicate sub-station locations in the form of transects or sampling points – the independence of which can be determined for the purposes of boosting replication in mixed effects analytical frameworks.
- To ensure independence between replicates, sampling stations should be located a minimum of 100m apart for sessile and sedentary species, and species that are mobile and move less than 100m within a 24-hour period.
- To ensure independence between replicates when sampling population or abundance estimates of large mobile taxa (for example cetaceans), sampling stations should be located a minimum of 1km apart when the responses to be measured are not behavioural and replicated at the level of the individual.
- Sub-stations should where possible be located 50m apart and no less than 10m apart for sedentary and sessile species, and mobile species that move less than 100m in a 24-hour period.
- The location of sampling stations should where possible, account for potential confounding environmental variables. Such variables might include (but are not limited to) gradients in wave and current exposure gradients, salinity, water clarity, river flow, and tidal exposure.
- Sampling duration and intervals should be designed taking into consideration the nature of the artificial light and noise pollution effects being assessed. For cyclical anthropogenic events such as traffic noise, for example, one should sample for 7+ days, to include the weekday-dependent changes in traffic intensity and timing in the sample. Continuous recording is not necessary, sampling at regular intervals is sufficient. When sampling a particular behaviour, or response to a specific noise/light event, sampling should be continuous with a predetermined recording time, to not miss any event. Examples include monitoring of sunrise/sunset-dependent behaviours.
- River habitat is a novel challenge for replicated sampling and ecological independence in the context of ALAN and noise pollution studies. Communities of migratory fish are not independent when sampled at different places in the same river, even when the above-distance measures are taken into account. Furthermore, the sampled specimen

at any particular passage in a river forms a moving target, and exposure conditions that are relevant and associated with the sample may as well be upstream or downstream from the sample location, at a distance depending on migration direction and speed. Monitoring studies will therefore target specific species to be able to relate detailed knowledge about their migratory ecology and seasonal timing to high-resolution LNP data at tailored geographic scales. Either tagged fish data can be used or observations of specific behaviours such as spawning, which may be audible for some species, acoustically detectable by Passive Acoustic Monitoring (in air and water), and which may reveal LNP-related fluctuations in the intensity of the behaviour. Larger community-broad samples may also be available, potentially in historical time series, which may also be explored at larger temporal and spatial scales.

Figure 1. Alternative approaches to designing LNP monitoring surveys of biological impacts. A. Samples are collected across ALAN and noise gradients that are not collinear. B. ALAN and noise are categorized as High and Low in a fully crossed design defining each of the treatment combinations A-D. C. ALAN and noise are scored using the risk mapping approach.

4. RESPONSES MEASURED

The following table (Table 2) is a list of the biological responses from the focused taxa/organisms/communities for each selected corresponding ecosystem and location.

Table 2. Biological responses measured where possible during AquaPLAN monitoring surveys

Partners	Ecosystems	Location(s)	Taxa	Responses	Units	EBV's measured
UOP	Temperate intertidal rocky shores	Plymouth Sound, UK Falmouth Bay, UK	<i>F. serratus</i> <i>F. vesiculosus</i> <i>F. spiralis</i> <i>P. canaliculata</i> <i>A. nodosum</i> <i>P. vulgata</i> <i>P. depressa</i> <i>N. lapillus</i> <i>L. obtusata</i> <i>M. edulis</i> <i>C. maenas</i> <i>P. bernhardus</i>	Abundance	% cover $n\ m^{-2}$ $n\ min^{-1}$	Patterns and species distributions Population abundance Population Structure
UNIPI, SZN	Subtidal macroalgae and seagrass	Tuscan and Ligurian coasts, Italy	<i>P. oceanica</i> <i>Ericaria spp.</i>	Abundance	Shoots m^{-2} Thalli/Leaves length % cover	Patterns and species distributions Population abundance Population Structure
BIU	Tropical subtidal ecosystems	Gulf of Aqaba, Israel	Community composition	Species richness	None (indexes)	Patterns and species distributions

Partners	Ecosystems	Location(s)	Taxa	Responses	Units	EBV's measured
			measured via eDNA	Species evenness Relative abundance		Population abundance
LEIDEN	Temperate rivers	Dutch rivers	Migratory fish	Behavioural responses Passage rates Bank preference Abundance Species richness	Ethograms per unit time Spatial distribution	Behavioural changes Migration progress migration decisions Patterns and species distributions Population abundance
FVB	Temperate lakes	German lakes	Zooplankton	Diel Vertical Migration	Numbers and sizes of individuals in relation to vertical distribution (fractions of m)	Patterns and species distributions Population abundance

5. METADATA

All AquaPLAN researchers are expected to collect the following essential metadata (**Table 3**) to accompany their biological datasets. Sun and moon variables can be obtained from www.timeanddate.com or from other sources (e.g. [suncalc](#) and [moonlit](#) packages in R).

Table 3. Metadata to be collected as during AquaPLAN monitoring surveys

Variable	Format	Notes
Station_ID	APUOP-01	AP = AquaPLAN; UOP= Partner acronym; -01 =Station number
Sub-station_ID	APUOP-01-01	Additional identified '-01' for sub-station.
Date	dd/mm/yyyy	
Time	hh:mm:ss TZ	TZ = Time Zone (daylight saving to be specified)
Latitude	Decimal degrees	
Longitude	Decimal degrees	Locations west of Greenwich meridian to be specified as negative values.
Sampling Design	Gradient/Categorized/Risk	See Figure 1
Tidal range (marine only)	meters	Tidal range on the day of sampling
Tidal flow (marine only)	Ebb/Flood	
High tide time (marine only)	hh:mm:ss TZ	TZ = Time Zone (daylight saving to be specified)
Low tide time (marine only)	hh:mm:ss TZ	TZ = Time Zone (daylight saving to be specified)
River flow velocity (rivers only)	Distance per unit time (m s ⁻¹)	
River height (rivers only)	meters	Taken from the nearest height gauge
Moonrise time	hh:mm:ss TZ	Night before when day sampling
Moonset time	hh:mm:ss TZ	Night before when day sampling
% of lunar disk illuminated	%	
Sunrise time	hh:mm:ss TZ	On the night of night sampling
Sunset time	hh:mm:ss TZ	On the night of night sampling
Cloud cover (behavioural and)	Octas	0-8 scale; 0 = no cloud; 8 = full sky covered; 9 = mist/fog

Variable	Format	Notes
activity (sampling only)		
Rainfall	None/Light/Moderate/Heavy	
Temperature (in-air acoustic recordings only)	°C	During sampling (deploy HOBO or consult meteorological data)

6. DATA MANAGEMENT

All data will be collected and curated in accordance with the AquaPLAN Data Management Plan outlined in D1.4.

- For consistency and ease of interpretation, all biological data shall be reported using the variables outlined in **Table 4**.
- Data shall be stored in a secure location until made available to the AquaPLAN consortium and the public as per the Data Management Plan.
- All data collected as part of the monitoring surveys shall be made available to the AquaPLAN consortium by month 36.
- All data collected as part of the monitoring surveys shall be curated in a central database that is made available to the AquaPLAN consortium by month 40 (D3.9).
- All data collected as part of the monitoring surveys shall be available for meta-analysis from month 36 to be completed by month 44 (D3.10).
- Project participants who intend to disseminate their results must give at least 15 calendar days prior notice to other project participants (unless agreed otherwise), together with sufficient information on the results they intend to disseminate (GA Article 17 – Annex 5; CA - paragraph 8.4.2 Dissemination of own (including jointly owned) Results; D6.1 PDEC - paragraph 2.2.4 Communication and Dissemination of Results).

Table 4. Biological variables to collect as during AquaPLAN monitoring surveys

Variable	Format	Notes
Station_ID	APUOP-01	AP = AquaPLAN. UOP= Partner acronym. -01 =Station number
Sub-station_ID	APUOP-01-01	Additional identified '-01' for sub-station.
Date	dd/mm/yyyy	
Time	hh:mm:ss TZ	TZ = Time Zone (daylight saving to be specified)
Latitude	Decimal degrees	
Longitude	Decimal degrees	Locations west of meridian to be specified as negative values.
Sampling_Design	Gradient/Categorized/Risk	See Figure 1
Taxon	Species or group sampled	
Response_type	Abundance, Relative Abundance, Species Richness, Species Evenness, Activity (incl DVM)	Examples included here
Response_units	$n\ m^{-2}$, % cover, index, $n\ min^{-1}$, shoots m^{-2} , length (mm)	Examples included here
Response_value	Numerical value of response	

7. ETHICS

7.1 GENERAL CONSIDERATIONS

The AquaPLAN Ethics guidelines are outlined in D1.2. Monitoring activities will be carried out in line with the highest ethical standards and the applicable EU, international and national law on ethical principles following the CA rules (14. Ethics). The following activities that may be carried out as part of the monitoring activities will be subject to ethics review.

7.2 EXPERIMENTS ON ANIMALS (FISH, INVERTEBRATES, MARINE MAMMALS)

Ethics review will not be required for passive sampling techniques, or techniques in which no animals are harmed in the process of collecting data. Where consideration of ethics is required, investigators will consult with their institutional ethics committees and the AquaPLAN ethics committee to ensure that the planned activities have taken due consideration of ethics and are following the applicable EU, international and national law on ethical principles.

D3.3

Harmonised protocols for monitoring LNP impact in aquatic systems

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